

An aerial photograph of London, England, featuring the River Thames and the Tower Bridge. The city's dense urban landscape is visible, with various buildings and structures. The sky is a mix of blue and white, with scattered clouds. The overall tone is bright and clear.

LONDON POPULAR FINANCIAL REPORT

PREPARED BY

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1. GENERAL OVERVIEW

This comprehensive paper offers an in-depth analysis of London's popular financial report, The report reflects London's commitment to economic, social, and environmental well-being. Our analysis aims to explore the and implications of these diverse policy areas, providing a comprehensive perspective on London's financial and social landscape.

This paper focuses on how London Mayor's policies are designed, financed and implemented in the framework, by encapsulating the strategic priorities and fostering sustainable development.

London's popular financial report is more than a mere financial statement; it is a comprehensive document that captures the city's approach to governance and development. This paper seeks to show in a comprehensive and easy way the intricate threads of the report, displaying how financial information interacts with the city's health, sport, transport, jobs, culture, community, education, and environment policies.

Here we provide a brief explanation of the content of the report:

Consolidated Group Financial Information: The paper begins by introducing the consolidated group financial information, which forms the foundation of the report. It highlights London's economic performance, which is a crucial indicator of the city's overall health

Health Policy: London's approach to health policy is analyzed, demonstrating how the financial report reflects the city's investments and strategies in healthcare

Sport Policy: The report also delves into London's sport policy, showing the investments in sports infrastructure, programs, and events. It discusses how these investments enhance the city's sporting landscape and contribute to the well-being of its residents

Transport Policy: The paper examines London's transport policy, providing informations regarding transportation infrastructure development, investments in public transit, and efforts to improve urban mobility. These investments are essential to the city's economic growth and quality of life

Jobs Policy: London's strategies for job creation and workforce development are discussed, highlighting the Mayor's commitment to develop employment opportunities and economic prosperity

Culture Policy: The report explores London's culture policy, demonstrating how funds allocations support cultural events, and creative initiatives that enhance the city's cultural and artistic heritage. It reflects the importance of cultural vibrancy to London's identity and appeal.

Community Policy: The paper investigates London's community policy, emphasizing the commitment of the Mayor to build a strong and inclusive community

Education Policy: London's education policy is analyzed, showing the investments in education, educational institutions, and programs that contribute to human capital development

Environment Policy: The report highlights London's commitment to environmental sustainability through its environmental policy. It emphasizes the effort the Mayor's has put over the years and that is still committed to follow by investing in environmental protection, sustainability initiatives, and measures to combat climate change.

SADIQ KHAN

MAYOR OF LONDON

BIOGRAPHY

Sadiq Khan was born in London and has lived here all his life. His parents moved to London from Pakistan in the 1960s. He was state-school educated in Tooting before studying Law at the University of North London. Sadiq and his wife have two daughters.

GOAL

The Mayor wants London to be a '**city for all Londoners**'. His work includes:

- Making it easier for people to move in and around the city.
- Improving London's environment
- Helping the capital's businesses to thrive
- Providing Londoners with more affordable housing
- Giving young people in London more opportunities

MAYOR'S ROLE

The role of the Mayor of London

The Mayor of London sets the budget and is responsible for making London a better place for everyone who visits, lives or works in the city. The Mayor is elected every four years.

3. LONDON ASSEMBLY

The **25 London Assembly Members**, elected alongside the Mayor, are *responsible for ensuring that promises made to Londoners are upheld*. This Assembly, with 11 members representing the entire capital and 14 elected by constituencies, serves as a key instrument in holding the Mayor, the most influential directly-elected UK politician.

The Assembly has a **Chair and Deputy Chair**, chosen by its members for one-year terms each April. The current Chair of the London Assembly in charge is Andre Boff. The Chair plays a central role in managing the Assembly's proceedings, including overseeing Mayor's Question Time and Plenary sessions. They ensure that meetings are conducted fairly, efficiently, and on schedule, make decisions on the order of business and speaking order for members, and manage other aspects of meeting logistics. In addition to their procedural responsibilities, the Chair represents the London Assembly at various internal and external events, such as Holocaust Memorial Day and Remembrance Service.

They actively promote the Assembly's role and work through social media, media interviews, and engagement with stakeholders, including Londoners. The Chair fulfills these duties while also handling their regular responsibilities of representing the interests of Londoners and their committee assignments.

The London Assembly holds regular **Committee meetings** to publicly discuss key issues that affect Londoners. These meetings are split into investigation areas, with cross-party Members working on them. Such committees are: *Audit Panel, Budget and Performance Committee, Confirmation Hearings Committee, Cost of Living Working Group, Economy Committee, Environment Committee, Fire Resilience and Emergency Planning Committee, GLA Oversight Committee, Health Committee, Housing Committee, Planning and Regeneration Committee, Police and Crime Committee, Transport Committee*

4. GENERAL INFORMATION

1

PEOPLE

1° place in the 2023 World's Best Cities Ranking

9 MILLION

Total population; Expected to reach 10 millions by 2038

58%

of births in London are from mother born overseas

2

ECONOMY

8° place in the The 2021 STC Economic Power Index

\$468 MILLIONS

Total worth of London Economy, accounting for:

24% of UK economic output

£78,000

Average GVA per job

40%

higher than UK average

3

PLACE

1° place in the IESE Cities in Motion Index 2022

32

Boroughs councils

48-51%

of London's landmass is 'green' or 'blue'

160,000

hectars covered

5. CONSOLIDATED GROUP

The **annual budget**, strategically allocating resources within the *Greater London Authority (GLA)* composed of:

- *Transport for London (TFL)*
- *Mayor's Office for Policing and Crime (MOPAC)*
- *London Fire Commissioner (LFC)*
- *London Legacy Development Corporation (LLDC)*
- *Old Oak and Park Royal Development Corporation (OPDC)*

01 MOPAC

Works on behalf of Londoners to fund and hold the Metropolitan Police Service **(MPS) to account, reduce crime and improve the provision of criminal justice services** across the capital.

02 TFL

Oversees the **planning, execution, and daily management of the city's public transit system** including buses, underground, overground, DLR, trams, and river services. Additionally, TfL manages road user charging schemes, maintains major roads and traffic signals, regulates taxis, promotes pedestrian and cycling initiatives.

03 LFC

Is responsible for **fire and rescue services in London** and supporting the London boroughs in their emergency planning role. It oversees the work of the London Fire Brigade (LFB).

04 LLDC

Is responsible for **promoting and delivering physical, social, economic and environmental regeneration** in Queen Elizabeth Olympic Park (QEOP) and surrounding area.

05 OPDC

Is responsible for the **Old Oak and Park Royal Opportunity Area to deliver the strategic regeneration opportunity**, creating an inclusive and accessible new urban district.

Fig. 0: Here, is displayed the gross expenditure for the GLA Group in % on a total of £14,959,838,928

5.1 EXPENSES AND TAX REVENUES

The finances of GLA Group come from many different sources of revenues; The gross expenditure for the GLA (Mayor and Assembly), and each functional body is funded through a combination of resources directly controlled and allocated by the Mayor, primarily:

- **Council tax:** the 33 local authorities will retain a part of the eligible growth
- **Retained business rates income:** GLA's local retention pilot under which the GLA retains 37 per cent of business rates growth, net of its tariff payment and any levy on growth
- **Fund surplus:** council tax collection fund surplus for 2021-22 of £9.8

Other sources of income, such as specific and general government grants and fares income, as well as locally raised taxes and charges, such as the congestion charge, the Crossrail Business Rate Supplement (BRS) and Mayoral Community Infrastructure Levy (MCIL).

Fig. 1

	Mayor	Assembly	MOPAC	LFC	TfL	LLDC	OPDC	Group items	Total
2022-23	£m	£m	£m	£m	£m	£m	£m	£m	£m
Council tax	66.7	2.7	849.5	180.7	52.5	0.0	0.0	61.5	1,213.6
Collection fund surplus (Ctax)	-0.6	0.0	-7.2	-1.6	-0.1	0.0	0.0	9.8	0.3
Business rates	125.3	5.1	65.4	242.7	1,897.0	29.3	6.8	918.9	3,290.4
Total Mayoral funding	191.3	7.8	907.7	421.8	1,949.4	29.3	6.8	990.2	4,504.3

Fig 2

Spending plans and council tax requirements	2022-23 £m	2022-23 %
Spending plans	14,950.3	100%
<i>Less funding sources:</i>		
Fares income	-4,474.2	30%
Extraordinary Grants	-1,241.5	8%
Home Office Police General and Formula Grant	-2,278.4	15%
Other general income	-2,307.3	15%
Retained business rates	-2,339.6	16%
Home Office specific grants for policing	-655.7	4%
Other specific government grants	-459.3	3%
Use of reserves	19.6	0%
2020-21 council tax surplus	-0.3	0%
Consolidated council tax requirement for GLA Group	1,213.6	8%

Forecast of the **GLA group council tax** precept income (**the 'consolidated council tax requirement'**) and the other sources of finance for 2022-23, including government grants and fare revenues, are summarised in this table

5.2 BALANCE SHEET AND RESERVES

We also also publish the **summary of the GLA's Balance Sheet at 31 March 2022**, comparing the position to a year ago; This is a 'snapshot' of the assets, liabilities, cash balances and reserves at the year-end date. Moreover, we show also a summary of the GLA's usable and unusable reserves at 31 March 2022, comparing the position to a year ago

Fig. 3

As at 31 March:	2022	2021
	£m	£m
Assets	6,379	7,163
Liabilities	(7,426)	(7,728)
Net Liabilities	(1,046)	(565)

The reduction in assets of £784m is largely **due to the net impact of the phasing of the repayment of 2020/21 and 2021/22 collection fund deficits** to billing authorities arising primarily from Covid-19 pandemic business rates reliefs which are funded through grants received from the Department of Levelling Up, Housing and Communities (DLUHC); offset by a net increase of £487m in investments, mainly in Residential Mortgage Backed Securities.

Fig.4

As at 31 March:	2022	2021
	£m	£m
Usable Reserves	(4,480)	(5,405)
Unusable Reserves	5,526	5,970

Usable reserves decreased by £925 million, mainly due to pandemic-related factors and the withdrawal of £132 million from a grant. **Unusable reserves** are earmarked for specific accounting purposes, primarily related to capital projects, and will be reduced over the next two decades as the associated borrowing is repaid.

6. HEALTH POLICY

The Mayor is dedicated to enhancing the health and wellbeing of Londoners, and introduced the **London Health Inequality Strategy Plan 2018-2028** which consists in 6 main programmes.

POLICIES AND PROGRAMMES

1. Healthy Children: This involves an **advertising ban on unhealthy food and restricting hot food takeaways near schools**.

The Child Obesity Taskforce drives action, promoting water-only policies in primary schools and implementing School Streets to improve children's health.

2. Healthy Minds: Efforts include **grants for community projects supporting mental health**, widespread suicide prevention training, the expansion of the Good Thinking initiative, and funding for the Young Londoners Fund to enhance mental health support.

Fig. 5: Life and healthy life expectancy data for London

Indicator	London		England	
	Men	Women	Men	Women
Life expectancy at birth ⁽¹⁾ (2017-19)	80.9 years	84.7 years	79.8 years	83.4 years
Healthy life expectancy at birth (2017-19)	63.5 years	64 years	63.2 years	63.5 years
Inequality in life expectancy at birth (2017-9) ¹⁰	7.2 years	5.1 years	9.4 years	7.6 years
Inequality in life expectancy at age 65 (2017-9) ¹¹	4.5 years	3.4 years	4.9 years	4.7 years

Fig. 6: Ranked risk factors driving the most death and disability in London:

3. Healthy Places: The Grow Back Greener Fund **supports green and climate-resilient projects**, and the London Healthy Workplace Award, Good Work Standard, and Living Wage accreditation promote fair work practices. Accommodation for those in need was secured during COVID-19, contributing to infection control and improved lives.

4. Healthy Communities: London leads in HIV diagnosis and treatment, with a commitment to reducing late diagnosis. **Efforts against HIV stigma are supported through Fast Track Cities. A Hepatitis C routemap and testing initiatives for the homeless** were established, and Dementia Friendly London initiatives enhance support for those with dementia.

5. Healthy Living: The Smoke Free coordination board **aims to make London smoke-free by 2030**. Funding has been secured for drug and alcohol support for rough sleepers, including detoxification and rehabilitation services.

The Mayor of London has unveiled his "**Sport for All of Us**" strategy, which aims to make London the world's most active and socially-integrated city. This strategy combines community sports and major sporting events to promote social integration, increase physical activity among Londoners, strengthen communities, and enhance London's status as a top destination for major sporting events.

Our work in sport has two distinct strands:

London: sports capital of the world

London has a strong tradition of hosting major sports events, with notable examples like the 2012 Olympics, 2015 Rugby World Cup, and 2017 World Athletics. These events offer economic and social advantages, such as international promotion, community sports programs, and volunteering opportunities. The city continues to excel in hosting global events, which is vital for its economy. The Mayor's approach **involves maximizing economic and social benefits through a sports events framework**, ensuring strong returns on investment, attracting more events through London & Partners, and using the Major Sports Events Engagement Fund to extend community benefits.

Sport Unites: community of sport

London's community sport focus is shifting toward promoting social integration with the 'Sport Unites' program, backed by an £8.8 million investment and an additional £3 million from the Mayor's Young Londoners Fund.

- Theme One: Sport for Social Integration

The Mayor aims to make social integration a clear goal of his sports program

- Theme Two: Active Londoners

The investment aims to expand local sports opportunities for Londoners, focusing on inactive individuals and creating pathways for various fitness goals

- Theme Three: Workforce, Tech & Capacity Building

Strengthening the community sports workforce and organizational skills, along with leveraging technology, are vital goals for Sport Unites and London's sports sector.

Fig. 7: Percentage of the London population participating in sport

8. TRANSPORT POLICY

The Mayor's Transport Strategy employs the **Healthy Streets Approach**, prioritizing health and personal experience in city planning. This approach will be applied across the entire transport system to achieve three main goals:

Fig. 8: MODE SHARE 2015, AND 2041 (EXPECTED)

1. **Healthy Streets and Healthy People:** By making streets more vibrant and pedestrian-friendly, the **quality of life for all London residents will improve, as streets constitute 80% of public spaces.**

2. **A Good Public Transport Experience:** Enhancing public transport services, **with a seamless and attractive "whole-journey" experience**, offers a viable alternative to car usage for longer distances.

3. **New Homes and Jobs:** With London needing 65,000 new homes annually and 1.3 million more jobs by 2041, **this strategy aims to reshape the city's growth** in a way that enhances everyone's quality of life.

Adopting the Healthy Streets Approach offers a range of benefits. Research indicates that if every Londoner engaged in just 20 minutes of daily walking or cycling, it could save the **NHS £1.7 billion** in treatment costs over the next 25 years. This includes:

1. 85,000 fewer hip fractures treated.
2. 19,200 fewer cases of dementia.
3. An estimated 18,800 fewer cases of depression.

Beyond health advantages, this approach can: reduce air and noise pollution, enhance mental well-being, combat social isolation, boost local economies, particularly on high streets.

8.1 HEALTHY STREET APPROACH

To implement the strategy effectively, London needs to adapt to technological changes, improve funding efficiency, collaborate with stakeholders, and enact specific action plans:

1. Bus Action Plan: Aiming for zero-carbon, comfortable, safe, and convenient bus travel.

2. Cycling Action Plan: Promoting cycling as an inclusive transportation mode.

3. Freight and Servicing Action Plan: Supporting safe, clean, and efficient freight movement while reallocating road space for walking, cycling, and public transport.

4. Vision Zero Action Plan: Striving to eliminate street fatalities and injuries for safer roadways.

5. Walking Action Plans: Focused on making London a highly walkable city, increasing walking trips and enhancing the pedestrian experience.

Fig. 9: EXPECTED MORE SHARE OUTCOMES, 2041

Fig 10: VOLUME OF CAR TRIPS THAT COULD BE MADE BY WALKING, CYCLING AND PUBLIC TRANSPORT

9. JOBS POLICY

The Mayor is committed to supporting London's business environment, with a focus on skilled employees being crucial to the city's economy. The Mayor's key priorities for jobs and skills include:

- 1. Enabling all Londoners to access education and skills**
- 2. Addressing the current and future requirements of London's economy and employers.**
- 3. Implementing a comprehensive city-wide program for technical skills and adult education.**

The Mayor's Skills Academies Programme, aims to help Londoners hardest hit by the pandemic, find jobs in key sectors for the city's recovery. It's funded with **£44 million** from various sources, including the Mayor of London, LEAP (the Local Enterprise Partnership for London). The program coordinates training and offers support to newly skilled individuals, building on the **Mayor's Workforce Integration Network** to remove barriers to quality job opportunities for underrepresented groups in London.

The objectives of the Mayoral Skills Academies program include:

- 1. Filling job vacancies** in priority sectors with skilled workers
- 2. Increasing the visibility of these sectors** to potential applicants
- 3. Facilitating Londoners' access to good work** in the identified sectors

Fig.11: Employee jobs below the the London Living Wage (LLW) vs employee jobs below the UK Living Wage (UKLW)

Fig. 12: Young people (18-24) not in Education, Employment or Training

4. Supporting the further education sector in delivering industry-relevant education

5. Gaining insights into priority sectors and assisting specific groups, such as young black men, in overcoming entry barriers

6. Helping employers address structural barriers in engaging, recruiting and retaining, with the Workforce Integration Network (WIN) toolkit.

The Culture Strategy, part of the Mayor's comprehensive plans, aims to create an inclusive city that emphasizes culture for all Londoners. It focuses on **four key priorities**:

- Love London:** London, a global city with a rich cultural history, faces accessibility and representation challenges. The *Mayor's London Borough of Culture competition* promotes community involvement through flagship projects and grassroots funding. These programs **strive to enhance cultural participation, diversify the creative workforce, support youth engagement, and strengthen community cohesion.**

Fig.13: % of respondents that have used/visited/engaged in the past 12 months

- Creative Londoners:** London's creative economy is crucial. However, challenges exist, including a decline in *arts education and diversity issues within the sector.* The Mayor **aims to support talent from diverse backgrounds, ensuring a workforce that mirrors the city's population and maintaining London's global leadership** in the creative industries.

- Culture and Good Growth:** London's fast-growing population, estimated to reach ten million by 2030, threatens culture and heritage preservation with the city losing numerous cultural venues. The Mayor **is investing £7 million in Creative Enterprise Zones to provide affordable space and support for artists**

Fig.14: Cultural space closures and new openings 2018-2022

- World City:** the Mayor's vision for London is to be an open, inclusive, and welcoming city that embraces international talent and investment. This includes supporting a *robust immigration system to accommodate students, short-term workers, and entrepreneurs.* **The goal is to maintain a vibrant, diverse, safe, and accessible 24-hour city.**

11. COMMUNITY POLICY

5 GENDER EQUALITY

11 SUSTAINABLE CITIES AND COMMUNITIES

A successful city needs to work well for all residents. Everyone should be able to share in its prosperity, culture and community life regardless of their age, social class, disability, race, religion, gender, gender identity, sexual orientation, marital status, or whether they are pregnant or on maternity leave.

The Mayor's **Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Strategy** outlines his commitment to fostering a more equitable, integrated city where everyone can realize their potential and feel welcomed. In *November 2022*, new equality objectives were introduced, supplanting those from the 2018 publication 'Inclusive London.'

The strategy is made up of *six parts*:

- A **great place to live**: the Mayor is committed to affordable housing to prevent poverty and homelessness. He focuses on inclusive, sustainable growth and addresses health issues like air pollution and fuel poverty.
- A **great place for young people**: The Mayor is determined to eliminate child poverty, reduce health and educational disparities, and improve access to quality schools in London.
- A **great place to work and do business**: The Mayor is focused on reducing labor market inequalities and fostering diversity through initiatives like the Skills for Londoners fund, the Good Work Standard, and support for entrepreneurs.
- **Getting around**: The Mayor is committed to Healthy Streets, emphasizing safety, inclusivity, affordability, and accessibility, to encourage walking, cycling, and public transport use for a better city life.
- A **safe, healthy and enjoyable city**: To create a more inclusive London, the Mayor is addressing crime, health disparities, and barriers to community participation. He's also working to improve cultural access and promote engagement for all residents, fostering social integration and a better quality of life in the city.
- **Leading by example**: The Mayor emphasizes workforce diversity within the Greater London Authority (GLA) group and advocates for a culture of respect, inclusivity, and support for employees' well-being. This extends to promoting diversity in procurement, supply chain engagement, and accessible communication to celebrate London's diverse communities.

Our mission is to work with children and young people, their family and friends, and our network of partner organisations, professionals, schools and services to make it happen.

Our objectives:

- children and young people to have good mental health and physical wellbeing
- children and young people to have a positive and well-rounded education
- young people to experience great opportunities to gain greater confidence, communication and aspiration
- young people to benefit from a skills route that leads to a job
- young people to feel empowered to shape and lead with stronger relationships with parents, teachers, youth practitioners and peers.

Fig. 15: Percentage of 16 and 17 year olds who are not in education, employment or training (NEET) or whose destination is unknown

Better teachers for London

Research evidence consistently finds that the **quality of teaching is a primary driver of educational outcomes.**

In addition to developing the school workforce, school leaders play a vital role in setting and mobilizing staff around a shared vision for their schools, and in developing the right cultures, practices and systems to improve attainment and progression.

The Mayor of London is working to support excellent teaching and leadership, and to build capacity in London's education system.

Inspiring the next generations:

We all remember our favorite teacher. It's amazing to have that kind of an impact on a young person's life. As a teacher, you could too.

London's a fantastic city to be a teacher. In fact, we've got some of the best schools in the country. And we've also got some of the best training opportunities for budding teachers like you.

13. ENVIRONMENT POLICY

London's environment is integral to the city's quality of life, impacting health, businesses, and daily operations. The **London Environment Strategy** outlines a vision for cleaner air, more green spaces, and addressing environmental challenges to create a *greener, healthier, and future-ready city*.

This strategy is a comprehensive approach to improve London's environment with immediate and long-term goals, focusing on people's quality of life. It emphasizes the need for collective efforts over the years to create a healthier and more desirable environment for Londoners.

01 Climate change and energy	02 Waste	02 Adapting to climate change	04 Green infrastructure	05 Air quality	06 Noise
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CLIMATE CHANGE AND ENERGY

The Mayor's initiatives encompass **promoting energy efficiency in homes and public buildings**, targeting low-income households to address fuel poverty and enforce landlord regulations. The plans also involve expanding communal heat networks, increasing solar capacity, establishing an energy supply company, and exploring low-carbon technologies and cost-effective insulation solutions.

GREEN INFRASTRUCTURE

The Mayor is taking a transformative approach to enhance London's green spaces. This includes **designating London as the first National Park City, increasing tree planting and green space improvement**, using an Urban Greening Factor, protecting the Green Belt, and establishing a London Green Spaces Commission. *The goal is to unlock the economic and environmental value of green infrastructure, ultimately improving the quality of life for all Londoners.*

WASTE

The Mayor's waste management initiatives include setting recycling standards, implementing pollution reduction measures, and reducing food and packaging waste by **50% by 2030**. These efforts involve designing out waste, promoting shared waste collection services, supporting waste reduction businesses and seeking improved recycling performance. *The goal is to transform London's approach to waste, conserving resources and minimizing its environmental impact.*

AIR QUALITY

The Mayor's plan includes phasing out fossil fuels, introducing the Ultra Low Emission Zone, and using an **Air Quality Positive standard for new building developments to improve air quality**. Additionally, efforts will be made to ensure that schools are not located in poor air quality zones, provide information on air pollution, set stringent air quality standards. *The goal is to prioritize public health by exceeding legal requirements to swiftly improve London's air quality.*

ADAPTING TO CLIMATE CHANGE

The Mayor's efforts aim to enhance London's resilience to climate-related challenges. This includes **better preparation for flooding, securing sustainable water resources**, advocating for a new Thames Barrier, reducing water leakages, providing alerts during extreme weather events, promoting climate-resilient developments. *The objective is to safeguard Londoners and create a fairer city in the face of global environmental issues.*

NOISE

The Mayor is committed to **several initiatives to address noise-related** challenges in London. These include opposing Heathrow Airport expansion, reducing traffic, and improving technology for quieter rail trains on the TfL network. Additionally, efforts to provide green and tranquil spaces in the city aim to offer respite from noise. *The overall objective is to enhance the city's livability and the well-being of its residents.*

14. METHODOLOGICAL NOTE & DISSEMINATION PLAN

METHODOLOGICAL NOTE

This report has been drafted by Federico Cordero and Ralf Karam, two undergraduate students of the University of Turin.

In order to show and explain the results and policies adopted by the Mayor in order to pursue the goal of making London a better place to live, we have chosen to form and deliver the London Popular Financial Report, an instrument that enhances the accessibility of informations and transparency about the policies, as well as an exchange of opinions between the government and the citizens;

- People should be informed and involved in the strategy to make London a better city -

The draft of the report has been done starting from an in depth analysis of the numerous policies adopted by the Mayor as well as processing data regarding the most relevant metrics, with the aim of making it simple and accessible for everybody interested. Moreover, this report has been created by following an approach based on scientific literature on the theme.

In particular, the bases of the paper is the six capital approach, composed of: human capital, natural capital, social capital, intellectual capital, productive capital and financial capital. In addition, the report has also been drafted by taking into account the 17 SDGs goals collected in United Nations Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development, in order to show the commitment of the city with the objectives of such Agenda.

The report is surrounded by statistical data in form of graphs and charts taken directly by the London Datastore as well as from some external institutions. The aim is providing a context regarding financial and non-financial performances of the city.

DISSEMINATION PLAN

In order to share the informations in this report to every citizen, to engage the population in the government choices, the diffusion of such report will happen through digital distribution and through the usual channels of distribution, such as:

- Official website of the municipality,
- Facebook
- Instagram
- LinkedIn
- Twitter
- Tv presentation
- Live presentation in an event

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